

ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS. PART V.
2-HYDROXY-3-NAPHTHOIC ACIDS: DETERMINATION OF COBALT

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Analytical properties of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and its nitro, bromo, iodo, acetyl and nitroso derivatives have been studied. Thorium and zirconium form more or less quantitative precipitates with all these acids. The nitro derivative affords almost a quantitative precipitate with titanium as well. The nitroso derivative could be used for the determination of cobalt, palladium and uranium in addition to thorium. The gravimetric determination of cobalt and its separation from nickel and other elements with the nitroso derivative have been described.

The analytical uses of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and its derivatives were previously studied (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 257, 394). In the present communication, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and its bromo, iodo, nitro, acetyl and nitroso derivatives have been examined for their analytical properties. All these compounds produce quantitative precipitation of thorium and zirconium. The dinitro derivative may be used for the quantitative estimation of titanium. The nitroso compound forms red, red-brown and orange precipitates with cobalt, palladium and uranium respectively. These metals may be determined gravimetrically with this reagent. The preparation of the derivatives of 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and the use of 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid in the quantitative estimation of cobalt have also been described in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagent grade (B.D.H.) 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was crystallised repeatedly from alcohol until its melting point rose to 222°. The derivatives of this acid were prepared from it by adopting the following methods.

4:6-Dinitro-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—Hydroxynaphthoic acid (18 g.) was taken in a large conical flask and to it was added about 25 c.c. of fuming nitric acid slowly with agitation of the flask and cooling under the tap after each addition. Vigorous reaction took place. After the reaction had subsided, about 500 c.c. of water was added to the mass and boiled for 10 minutes. The mixture was filtered after cooling, and washed with water. The reddish orange dinitro compound was crystallised from water, m. p. 138°. (Found: N, 10.23. Calc. for $C_{11}H_6O_7N_2$: N, 10.07 %).

1-Bromo-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—Hydroxynaphthoic acid (18 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of absolute alcohol and cooled in ice. To this was added dropwise with stirring bromine (5 %, 8 g.) in glacial acetic acid solution, maintaining the temperature of the mixture below 10° during bromination. The mixture was then poured on a large volume of water when a pale yellow voluminous precipitate formed, which on stirring was converted into a gummy mass. The mass was extracted with ether and then dissolved in alcohol, after removing the ether. On pouring the alcoholic solution on cold water, a voluminous yellow precipitate was formed, m.p. 165°. (Found: Br, 29.04. Calc. for $C_{11}H_7O_3Br$: Br, 29.96 %).

1:6-Di-iodo-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—To a solution of hydroxynaphthoic acid (1 mole) in alcohol, cooled in ice, was slowly added a freshly prepared solution of ICl in glacial acetic acid (5%) with constant stirring. The mixture was kept in darkness for about 15 minutes and then it was poured on a large volume of water. The resulting voluminous yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water and crystallised from alcohol (1:1), m.p. 215°. (Found: I, 57.2. Calc. for $C_{11}H_6O_3I_2$: I, 57.7%).

2-Acetyl-3-naphthoic Acid.—To hydroxynaphthoic acid (18 g.) in a dry conical flask were added 25 c.c. of acetic anhydride and then 3 drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.). The mixture was shaken for half-an-hour and then heated on a water-bath for 15 minutes until the solution became clear. It was cooled and cold water was added to the mass, filtered and washed with water. The white solid, thus obtained, was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185°.

1-Nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid.—A method similar to that for the synthesis of 1-nitroso- β -naphthol (Marvel and Patter, "Organic Synthesis", 1922, 2, p. 61) was adopted for the preparation of this reagent with a little modification. Hydroxynaphthoic acid (36 g.) was dissolved in NaOH solution (10%, 10 g.) in water, with the aid of heat. It was cooled and diluted to 200 c.c. with water. The solution was then further cooled to 0° by a freezing mixture. $NaNO_2$ (18 g.) in water (50 c.c.) was then added with vigorous stirring. To this mixture, now kept at 0° by adding crushed ice from time to time, was added dilute sulphuric acid very slowly with stirring, till the solution became acidic to Congo red. 1-Nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid separated in the form of a brick-red precipitate. The stirring was continued for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour more. The product was filtered, washed with water and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 190 (Found: N, 6.11. Calc. for $C_{11}H_7O_4N$: N, 6.45%).

Possible Use in Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis

Stock molar solutions of Ag, Hg (ous and ic), Pb, Cu, Cd, Bi, Sb, Sn, Fe (ous and ic), Al, Cr, Mn, Zn, Co, Ni, Ca, Ba, Sr, Mg, Pd, Th, Zr, U, V, Th and Pt were prepared from their soluble salts. To 1 c.c. each of the salt solution were added 2 c.c. of the acetate buffer and 1% solution of the reagent in hot water or alcohol (1:1). For p_K higher than 7, ammoniacal solutions, where possible, were used. The colour change or precipitation was noted in each case. The washed precipitates were examined for the presence of the metal by decomposing them with concentrated mineral acids and applying standard tests. To examine the complete precipitation, the filtrate from the washed precipitate, obtained by the addition of the reagent in excess, was tested for the absence of the cation. The results of such tests with the reagents prepared are summarised below.

(1). *2-Hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid*: Alcoholic solution produced blue and orange coloration with Fe^{III} and U at p_K 1.8 and higher. Th and Zr formed quantitative precipitation in presence of ammonium acetate at p_K 3.5. These salts are soluble in dilute acids, ammonium carbonate and in excess of ammonium acetate, but insoluble in alcohol. Precipitations of Hg^I , Pb and Ce^{IV} were not quantitative.

(2). *4:6-Dinitro-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid*: Hg^I , Pb and Ce^{IV} formed yellow, yellowish white and deep yellow precipitate, respectively, at p_H 2.5 and even lower. Precipitation with Ce^{IV} was quantitative. Ti, Th and Zr also gave yellow quantitative precipitation at p_H 3. Mn and Al showed a slight turbidity at p_H 7.5 and 2.5 respectively. Fe^{III} produced a brownish red coloration at p_H 2, which deepened on boiling. Titanium salt was slightly soluble, while those of Ce^{IV} , Th and Zr were completely insoluble in hot water.

(3). *1-Bromo-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid*: Alcoholic solution produced bluish green and pale blue coloration with Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} respectively. Similar precipitates, as obtained with reagent No. 1, were also obtained with Hg^I , Pb and Ce^{IV} in this case. Precipitations, however, were incomplete. Thorium and zirconium formed colorless salts.

(4). *1:6-Di-iodo-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid*: Hg^I , Pb and Ce^{IV} produced incomplete precipitation. Yellow precipitates of Th and Zr were obtained with alcoholic solution. Such precipitation was quantitative.

(5). *2-Acetyl-3-naphthoic acid*: This reagent gave no coloration with Fe (ous & ic) and U and produced almost quantitative precipitation with Th and Zr.

(6). *1-Nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid*: Aqueous solution of the reagent showed green coloration with copper in ammoniacal solution. Hg^I formed a deep orange precipitate, sparingly soluble the hot; Hg^{II} formed a precipitate in the cold, changing to brown on boiling. Pb formed a yellow precipitate, soluble in the hot. Fe^{II} gave a green precipitate, while Fe^{III} , a brown colour. Be showed a yellowish green coloration, and on standing, a slight green precipitate. Cerium^{IV} ammonium sulphate indicated a slight turbidity, while a deep orange precipitate appeared with ceric nitrate. Cobalt in acetic acid medium produced a red precipitate, while Th, Zr, Pd and U formed pale orange, orange, red-brown and orange precipitation respectively within a p_H range 2 to 5. Precipitation of Ce^{IV} , Co, Th, Zr, Pd and U appeared to be quantitative. These salts are soluble in high acid concentration and several of them are even soluble in some organic solvents.

Determination of Cobalt with 1-Nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic Acid

Organic reagents for the determination of cobalt are many, of which mention may be made of anthranilic acid (Funk and Ditt, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 93, 241), 8-hydroxyquinoline (Fleck, *Analyst*, 1937, 62, 378), phenylthiohydantoic acid (Willard and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2119), pyridine (Spacu and Dick, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 71, 97) and tetraphenylarsonium chloride (Pepkowitz and Marley, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 1330).

Of the various derivatives of naphthol that have been used in the estimation of cobalt, α -nitroso- β -naphthol (Mayer and Feigl, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1932, 90, 15) has proved most effective. Other naphthol derivatives which are found to chelate with cobalt are: 2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate acid (Wise and Brandt, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 693)

nitroso-R-salt (McPherson and Stewart, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1938, **32**, 763), 2:7-dinitroso-chromotropic acid (Teigmann, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1943, **63**, 42), and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (Cheng and Bray, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 782). The use of 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, described in this paper, has been proved successful in the gravimetric estimation of cobalt and its separation from nickel and other foreign ions.

An 1% solution of 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid was prepared in hot water and filtered. A deep orange-coloured solution was obtained. A fresh solution was prepared daily.

The reagent (1 g.) was dissolved in 30 c.c. glacial acetic acid with the aid of heat; the solution was then diluted to 100 c.c. with water. A greenish orange solution resulted, which was filtered and then used. A stock solution of cobalt was prepared from the reagent grade $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and estimated by the standard method.

Cobalt Complex: Method I.—A solution of cobaltous chloride was diluted to 50 c. c. and was brought to boil; to this solution was added dropwise with stirring an 1% solution of the reagent in hot water, when a reddish brown precipitate appeared which on boiling for 2 minutes coagulated and collected towards the centre of the beaker. The precipitate was allowed to stand for 2 hours and then filtered in a weighed sintered crucible, washed with hot acetic acid (1:2) and then with boiling water. The cobalt salt was then dried in an electric oven at 130° to a constant weight.

Method II.—In this method Co^{II} was converted to Co^{III} by following the procedure of Mayer and Feigl (*loc. cit.*). A known volume of the standard cobalt solution was taken in a 250 c.c. beaker and 1 c. c. of 30 volume H_2O_2 was added to it, followed by dilute NaOH till the solution became distinctly alkaline. A brisk effervescence of oxygen took place and the beaker was kept covered with a clock glass. When the reaction had subsided, the black cobaltic oxide was dissolved by adding about 15 c.c. of glacial acetic acid with the aid of heat. The solution was then diluted to 100 c. c. and was brought to boil. To this was now added the solution of the reagent in acetic acid till the precipitation was complete. A deep red precipitate formed which was digested on a water-bath for 20 minutes. The precipitate was allowed to stand for one hour and then filtered through a sintered crucible, washed and dried similarly as in method I.

Composition of the Cobalt Salt.—In order to find out the composition of the cobalt complex, a weighed quantity of the salt (containing a few mg. of Co), prepared under methods I and II, was separately ignited carefully in a platinum crucible in an oxidising atmosphere at 750° - 850° , adding a few drops of HNO_3 towards the end. After cooling, the mass was weighed as cobalto-cobaltic oxide, Co_2O_4 . Cobalt in the salt was also determined as CoSO_4 (Vogel, "Quantitative Analysis", 1953, p. 459). The results of analysis have been recorded in Table I. The salt obtained by method I gave a composition, as cobalt: reagent ratio = 3:1. This indicates that the complex may have a formula: $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_6\text{O}_4\text{N})_3$. But the cobalt salt, obtained by method II seems to have the composition $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_6\text{O}_4\text{N})_4$ or more probably $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_6\text{O}_4\text{N})_3, (\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_6\text{O}_4\text{N})_2$ as the latter formula is more definite. Determination of Co^{II} after its oxidation with H_2O_2 is preferable.

TABLE I

Analysis of cobalt complex.

Cobalt salt (dried at 130°).	Co found by		Co. (calc from salt).
	Ignition.	Sulphate	
	Salt obtained by method I.		
0.0246 g.	0.0016 g.	0.0018 g.	0.0020 g.
0.0310	0.0020	0.0022	0.0026
0.0538	0.0049	0.0042	0.0045
	Salt obtained by method II.		
0.0291	0.0016	0.0017	0.0019
0.0386	0.0021	0.0029	0.0025
0.0602	0.0035	0.0036	0.0038

Optimum Conditions for the Determination of Cobalt

H-ion Concentration.—With a view to studying the p_H ranges over which cobalt could be completely precipitated with this reagent by method II, p_H of the solution was varied by adding acetate buffer solution or ammonium chloride and ammonia. The precipitation was carried out as before, the salt weighed and the amount of cobalt calculated on the assumption that 4:1 reagent-cobalt complex formed. The suitable p_H range, thus observed, was from 2 to 4.7. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Effect of p_H on the precipitation of cobalt.

	Cobalt taken = 0.0032 g.							
p_H	1.3	2.1	2.8	3.4	4.2	4.7	5.3	
Co salt (g.)	0.0307	0.0528	0.0532	0.0529	0.0531	0.0525	0.0403	
Co found (g.)	0.00195	0.00336	0.00338	0.00370	0.00318	0.00334	0.00256	
Error (mg.)	-1.2	+0.2	+0.2	+0.2	+0.2	+0.1	-0.6	

Temperature of Drying.—It was found that the salt should be dried between temperatures 125° and 130° before weighing to get the results corresponding to the formula $(C_{11}H_6O_4N)_2 \cdot Co$, $(C_{11}H_7O_4N)_2$. The salt dried at various temperatures gave results shown in Table III. The composition of the salt becomes definite when it is dried at 130° or above.

TABLE III

Co taken.	Temp. of drying.	Co salt.	Co found (sulphate method).	Probable composition.
0.0064 g.	110°	0.1088 g.	0.0068 g.	$(C_{11}H_6O_4N)_4 \cdot Co$, H_2O
0.0064	115°	0.0976	0.0061	Do
0.0064	120°	0.1072	0.0067	Do
0.0064	125°	0.1075	0.0067	Do
0.0064	130°	0.1021	0.0065	$(C_{11}H_6O_4N)_2 \cdot Co$, $(C_{11}H_7O_4N)_2$
0.0064	140°	0.1036	0.0066	Do

Analytical Procedure.—A solution of cobalt containing about 5 mg. of cobalt, taken in a beaker, was diluted to about 30 c.c. and this was oxidised by adding a few drops of H_2O_2 (30 vol.). To this was added with stirring 0.1N-NaOH till the mixture became alkaline. The beaker was kept covered with a clock glass until the effervescence due to oxygen had ceased. The precipitated cobaltic oxide was dissolved with the aid of heat in the minimum quantity of acetic acid (1 : 1). The p_H of the solution was adjusted to 2.5 and then it was diluted to 100 c.c. This was boiled and to it was added an 1% solution of the reagent in dilute acetic acid. The precipitate was filtered, washed with dilute acetic acid and finally with hot water and dried in an electric oven at 130° to a constant weight. Co has been calculated from the formula: $(C_{11}H_5O_4N)_2 \cdot Co$, $(C_{11}H_5O_4N)_2$. The results have been compared with those obtained by estimating Co with anthranilic acid, and recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Co taken.	1-NO-2-OH-3-naphthoic acid.		Anthranilic acid.	
	Wt of Co salt.	Co calc.	Wt. of Co salt	Co calc.
0.0072 g.	0.1086 g.	0.0069 g.	0.0410 g.	0.0073 g.
0.0064	0.1083	0.0069	0.0354	0.0065
0.0048	0.0816	0.0052	0.0281	0.0050
0.0032	0.0565	0.0036	0.0185	0.0033
0.0024	0.0424	0.0027	0.0124	0.0022

Precipitation Limit.—The reagent was proved to be highly sensitive for cobalt. Cobalt was precipitated even from solutions having concentration $1 : 10^6$, below which only red coloration was produced. The reagent may be used for the qualitative detection of cobalt even in presence of nickel.

Separation from Nickel.—To a solution of cobalt an aliquot quantity of a standard nickel solution was added. Cobalt was determined in the mixture by following the same procedure. The results recorded in Table V indicate that an excessive amount of nickel, if present in the mixture, interferes in the determination of cobalt.

TABLE V

Metals present.	Co salt.	Co found.	Metals present.	Co salt.	Co found.
Co : 0.0024	0.0345 g.	0.0021 g.	Co 0.0048 g.	0.0836 g	0.0053 g.
Ni : 0.0036	...	...	0.0198	...	...
Co : 0.0024	0.0440	0.0028	0.0048	0.0911	0.0058
Ni : 0.0054	...	...	0.016	...	...
Co : 0.0024	0.0455	0.0029	0.0064	0.1193	0.0076
Ni : 0.0072	...	...	0.0288	...	...
Co : 0.0048	0.0832	0.0053	0.0064	0.0972	0.0081
Ni : 0.0180	...	...	0.0360	...	...

Effect of Diverse Ions.—A study was undertaken to determine which of the more common ions would interfere with the method. Cobalt was precipitated in presence of a large number of ions at p_H 2.5, by following the method I, as described before, and cobalt was determined as $CoSO_4$, as method II was time-consuming. Slight interference was noticed in case of Fe^{+++} and aluminium. Mercury, lead, beryllium, Fe^{++} ,

Ce^{IV}, thorium, zirconium, palladium and uranium, however, caused heavy interference as they were also co-precipitated more or less at the same p_H .

TABLE VI

Co taken = 0.0064g.			
Metal added.	Co found.	Metal added.	Co found.
Cu: 0.0312 g.	0.0068 g.	Ca: 0.0414 g.	0.0067 g.
Ba: 0.0205	0.0061	Sr: 0.0126	0.0067
Al: 0.0158	0.0069	Fe ^{III} : 0.0139	0.0071
Cr: 0.0247	0.0062	Mn: 0.0103	0.0060
Mg: 0.0271	0.0063	Zn: 0.0312	0.0061
Cd: 0.0137	0.0068	Bi: 0.0233	0.0067

CONCLUSION

Of the six organic compounds, the analytical properties of which have been described here, 1-nitroso-2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid has proved to be very useful in the gravimetric determination of cobalt. The composition of the cobalt complex of this acid is the same as that of the cobalt complex of α -nitroso- β -naphthol. It is seen that the -COOH group present in the compound most probably does not take any part in linking cobalt. The advantage of this acid over α -nitroso- β -naphthol is that the former is easily soluble in water and forms more voluminous precipitate of cobalt than the latter. Most of the common ions do not interfere in the determination and cobalt may be separated from a considerable amount of nickel. The reagent may also find possible use in the colorimetric determination of cobalt.

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